

Need to conserve wild rice species in Nepal

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A group of scientists from the Nepal Agricultural Research Council (NARC) and IRRI collaborated in exploring and collecting wild rice species in far-western, midwestern, and western Nepal in November 1998. Seventy-three samples representing *Oryza rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. granulata*, and weedy types were collected. *O. rufipogon* and *O. nivara* were found as small or large populations with a great morphological variation in a wide range of environments, such as lakes, swamps, ponds, along ditches and canals, and at the edge of or inside farmers' rice fields. *O. granulata* was a rare upland wild rice in Nepal found in partially shaded habitats in mountainous forests.

One *O. rufipogon* population was collected in Palpa at an altitude of nearly 900 m. It was the highest location recorded by the IRRI International Rice Genebank for this species collected from subcontinental countries. The species may have potential for cold tolerance. Another extensive population of *O. rufipogon* was observed in about 50 ha in Ajigara Lake in Kapilbastu. This lake was full of typical *O. rufipogon* and seemed to be a haven for wildlife, particularly birds. This area could be an ideal site for *in situ* conservation.

Nepali farmer helping collect weedy and wild rice in his field

The data indicated that wild rice species were declining in number and population size because of rapid changes in rice ecosystems and more extensive farming practices. Immediate action is needed to conserve the diversity of wild rice species in Nepal.

Adverse weather severely depletes seed supply of traditional varieties

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In November 1998, a team from the IRRI Genetic Resources Center and the Philippines Rice Research Institute (PhilRice) went to Cagayan Province in northeastern Philippines to take seeds back to farmers who had participated in the project titled "Safeguarding and Preservation of the Biodiversity of the Rice Genepool: Component II—On-Farm Conservation" funded by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation. The seeds had been collected from farmers in 1996 and planted and characterized at IRRI in 1997. A total of 28 varieties, including both modern and traditional types, were distributed to farmers in 15 villages. In all, 1.5 t of seed were distributed.

The timing of the trip was advantageous for Cagayano farmers because of the dire effects of El Niño in 1997 and typhoons Iliang and Loleng in 1998 on local seed stocks. Traditional varieties, such as the

popular *Wagwag* types, were especially hard hit by the catastrophes. Many farmers were not able to obtain *Wagwag* seeds in 1997 or 1998 due to poor seed storage capability, lack of a local or regional seed backup system, limited government intervention, and a general dearth of seeds available for farmer-to-farmer exchange.

Although data analysis is ongoing, it is clear that a formal mechanism for storing, growing, and distributing seeds of traditional varieties should be developed. GRC staff are currently working on proposals to enhance the seed supply system. By invigorating and formalizing this system, household food and economic security may be improved and the likelihood of on-farm conservation of traditional rice varieties will increase.

Outbreak of yellow stunt syndrome on rice in Punjab, India

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Yellow stunt syndrome on rice was first seen in the Tarsikka block of Amritsar District during 1996, and then in the Mehta block of Amritsar and Quadian block of Gurdaspur Districts of Punjab, India, in 1997. By 1998, the incidence, severity, and affected areas in these two districts increased considerably. Of about 490,000 ha planted to rice, nearly 40,000 ha were severely damaged (yield losses estimated to be between 30% and 100%). All recommended varieties, including Basmati types, were affected. According to local extension officers and farmers, symptoms were only visible 20-30 d after transplanting. Affected leaves were bright yellow with occasional orange leaf discoloration. Pronounced stunting of plants was common. Reduced tillering but no crinkling or streaking of leaves was observed. Roots of diseased plants showed poor growth with no galls. When incidence was high, the spread of diseased plants was uniform in the plot.